

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MAGNIFICENT
RANTASVIR DIRECTION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation The article contains information about the direction of majestic painting, its development, the appearance of the first magnificent paintings in Uzbekistan, the well-known master of painting, the People's Artist of Uzbekistan B. Jalolov.

Key words: majestic painting, fresco, stained glass, plafond, sgraffitto, panel
Man is an artist by nature. He strives to share with others what he has seen and known in his life, to describe and describe the beautiful nature and human beauty that he has seen.

I study at the institute in the field of painting. Did you know that painting is one of the great inventions of mankind? Pictures, figures, hearts, which are imprinted in history for a lifetime. He wants this moment of his life to be reflected with joy, with a smile on his face, in the majestic complexion of a person. Majestic painting combining styles such as fresco, mosaic, stained glass, and sgraffito has decorated buildings for several periods, and even today, interest in these styles is as relevant as ever. This type of art has been perfected over the centuries and continues to develop even today. This type of painting related to architecture cannot be self-explanatory. It is located on a certain surface and is in inseparable unity with the environment. After all, it reflects the harmonious combination of majestic paintings that have reached their development and the buildings where they are located, modern architectural structures.

The artist's spiritual world is reflected in his works. The thoughts of the artist, which he wants to convey to the viewer, are gathered and transferred to colors through fingers, and from colors to white fabrics, and a work of art is created. An artist gives a piece of his heart to a work created from the heart and cherishes it for a lifetime. Artists create works with the help of powerful painting tools, and they always use the possibilities of drawing and composition.

fresco , plafond, and display (panno). (mural painting). Majestic painting is an ancient art form, and paintings of primitive people on cave walls (for example, Zarautsoi paintings, etc.) are the first examples of it. It developed tremendously in the ancient and medieval ages and became one of the leading art forms. It was widely developed in ancient Egypt and Greece, and later in Byzantium and other countries, rare examples of majestic painting were created. It reached its real stage of development especially during the Renaissance. Michelangelo's murals for the Vatican Palace, Veronese's compositions are rare monuments of this period.

For example, this type of painting related to architecture has developed in Uzbekistan. the interior of the buildings, the ceilings, and partly the exterior of the building are shown in the images made on the walls. It should be noted that the form of a majestic work is primarily determined by its meaning and its place in the architectural complex or in the building itself. The task of harmonizing the characteristics of the architectural building that displays these works with the majestic paintings that are being created should always be the primary task.

The new stage of development of majestic painting in Uzbekistan corresponds to the 30-50s of the last century. From these years, the decoration of public and administrative buildings developed. Compositions were created on the nature of Uzbekistan, everyday life, science, and work, and pictures were drawn on plots taken from classic Uzbek literature (representations on the walls of the Navoi Theater building; authors Ch. Ahmarov, O. Tansikboev, V. Cheprakov,

etc.). In the 1960s and 1980s, high-level works were created in majestic color. Q. Saipov, B. Jalolov, I. Lipene, V. Burmakin and others created frescoes, mosaics, and stained glass works. In the years after the independence of Uzbekistan, the Majestic painting has been enriched with new national themes. Today, in Uzbekistan, the direction of majestic painting is rapidly developing as the most developed type of fine art. The more we talk about the particular school and its representatives, the less we say about it. One of them is Bahadir Jalolov. He is one of the well-known, highly recognized, recognized artists not only in Uzbekistan, but also internationally, whose work is constantly followed with admiration. B. Jalolov's works, magnificent creative works decorate museums and other cultural and educational buildings in our country, a number of embassies, collections and galleries abroad.

"The artist's works have spirit, mood, human psychology. His works encourage us to take a deep philosophical look at the relationship between man and the universe, controversial processes in existence, and life in general. "

The work of the master artist is so valuable that it fills every viewer with thoughts. The owner of the brush encourages people to listen to the thoughts that he has prepared to express through the picture, to think about it.

In conclusion, it should be noted that a person cannot live without perceiving beauty or striving for beauty. Until the human being felt the beauty of nature and society, he went through the history of long centuries of development and continued to be formed.

Many cave and rock carvings of animals recorded in the history of art reflect this development. Such images have improved over time, enriched in content and changed. The uniqueness and beauty of Afrosiyab and Varakhsha wall paintings of the early Middle Ages still amaze the audience.

During the era of the master Amir Temur and the Timurids, wall paintings and decorations of various contents added beauty to the magnificent buildings,

palaces and mosques, madrasas and mausoleums, and showed the magnificence of these buildings. After all, visual art, one of its unique types, the majestic painting, will strengthen its potential over time and continue to share pleasure with people.

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар рўйхати:

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